

3-Hydroxy-2-(2'-thienyl)-4H-chromen-4-one as an analytical reagent for the trace determination of cerium

Amita Garg and L. R. Kakkar*

Department of Chemistry, Kurukshetra University, Kurukshetra-136 119, India

E-mail : search@vidya.kuk.ernet.in; search@granth.kuk.ernet.in

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A simple and rapid method for the direct spectrophotometric determination of trace amounts of cerium(III) has been worked out using 3-hydroxy-2-(2'-thienyl)-4H-chromen-4-one (HTC) as a complexing agent in presence of diphenylamine with λ_{\max} at 430 nm. Several analytically important ions do not cause interference in the procedure. The method has good reproducibility and can be satisfactorily applied for the analysis of cerium containing samples.

Since cerium, in the trivalent state, has the same chemical properties as all the other rare earth elements, its determination particularly at the trace level is, therefore, difficult for the same reason. Most of the methods reported in the literature for cerium determination make use of various dyestuffs^{1,2}. Amongst them, chlorosulfophenol S³, diantipyrylvinylphenylmethane⁴, 4-(2-pyridylazo) resorcinol⁵, Methylthymol Blue⁶, sulpharsazen⁷, Alizarin Red S⁸, Bromopyrogallol Red⁹, triethylene tetraamine hexaacetic acid¹⁰, 3,4,5-trimethoxy-4'-Me-dibenzoyl-methane¹¹, calix[4]arene-5,11,17,23-tetrasulfonate¹², are though commonly employed for the purpose, but the procedures in general are found to be wanting in respect of sensitivity and selectivity besides adjustment of other experimental conditions. Taking in to consideration the problems encountered, an attempt has been made to develop a spectrophotometric method for the microdetermination of cerium employing 3-hydroxy-2-(2'-thienyl)-4H-chromen-4-one as a complexing agent with the following details.

Experimental

A stock solution of cerium(III), 1 mg ml⁻¹, is prepared by dissolving an accurately weighed amount of Ce(NO₃)₃·6H₂O in deionized water. Lower concentrations of the metal ion at the $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ level are obtained by suitable dilutions.

Solutions of other metal ions of appropriate concentration are prepared by dissolving their commonly available salts (A.R.) in water or dilute acids. A 1% (w/v) solution of diphenylamine is prepared in ethanol afresh daily. A 0.01% (w/v) solution of 3-hydroxy-2-(2'-thienyl)-4H-chromen-4-one (HTC)¹³, is prepared in ethanol.

Apparatus : For absorbance measurements, a UV-visible spectrophotometer (Shimadzu-UV-140-02) is used.

Procedure : To a sample solution containing 10 $\mu\text{g Ce}^{\text{III}}$ in a 10 ml measuring flask, add 1.0 ml of 1% diphenylamine, 1.0 ml of 0.01% HTC and enough deionized water to make up the volume (pH 8.5). The absorbance of the yellow coloured species is measured at 430 nm against a similarly prepared reagent blank and cerium content is determined

Table 1. Effect of various parameters on the absorbance of the cerium complex

1. Temperature, (°C) ^a	25	30*-40	45	50	55	60	
Absorbance	0.280	0.310	0.300	0.280	0.270	0.230	
2. Diphenylamine, (ml) ^b	0	0.2	0.5	0.8-1.5	1.6	1.8	2.0
(1% in ethanol)							
Absorbance	0.210	0.250	0.290	0.310	0.300	0.280	0.250
3. HTC, (ml) ^c	0	0.5	0.7	0.8-1.5	1.8	2.0	3.0
(0.01% in ethanol)							
Absorbance	0.020	0.230	0.300	0.310	0.290	0.270	0.180

*Room temperature.

^aCe^{III} = 10 μg , diphenylamine, 1% = 1 ml, HTC, 0.01% = 1.0 ml, temperature = variable, λ_{\max} = 430 nm. ^bCe^{III} = 10 μg , diphenylamine, 1% = variable, HTC, 0.01% = 1.0 ml; λ_{\max} = 430 nm, at room temperature. ^cCe^{III} = 10 μg , diphenylamine, 1% = 1 ml, HTC, 0.01% = variable, λ_{\max} = 430 nm, at room temperature.

from the standard curve drawn by plotting absorbance values corresponding to varying trace amounts of cerium following the proposed procedure.

Results and discussion

It has been found that Ce^{III} reacts with HTC forming a yellow coloured complex in presence of diphenylamine, whose λ_{max} lies at 430 nm. The absorbance measurements are effected in the aqueous phase as the resulting complex is non-extractable in nature.

The influence of temperature, diphenylamine and HTC on the formation and absorbance of the complex is shown in Table 1. It is evident from the data that for 10 μ g Ce, 0.8–1.5 ml of 1% diphenylamine and 0.8–1.5 ml of 0.01% HTC in a final 10 ml aqueous volume at RT are the optimum conditions for the formation of the complex with λ_{max} at 430 nm.

Effect of diverse ions :

The presence of anions such as sulphate, chloride, nitrate, thiourea, acetate, bromide, iodide, nitrite (10 mg each); tartrate, citrate, fluoride, thiocyanate (1 mg each); in 10 ml aqueous solution containing 10 μ g Ce, does not have any effect on the absorbance of the complex and are, therefore,

Table 2. Analysis of different samples by the proposed method

Sl. no.	Composition of the sample		
	Matrix ^a	Ce ^{III} added	Ce ^{III} found
		μ g	μ g
1.	Ce ^{IV} (0.5)	10	10
2.	Os ^{VIII} (0.5)	5	4.7
3.	As ^{III} (0.5)	7	6.6
4.	Mn ^{II} (0.01), Sb ^{III} (0.01)	9	8.7
5.	Pd ^{II} (0.01), Pt ^{IV} (0.01)	3	3
6.	Ru ^{III} (0.01), Se ^{IV} (0.01)	5	4.7
7.	Cr ^{VI} (0.01), Re ^{VII} (0.01)	3	2.1
8.	Pd ^{II} (0.01), Pt ^{IV} (0.01), As ^{III} (0.5)	7	6.6
9*	La ^{III} (0.05), Th ^{IV} (0.01), Pr ^{III} (0.012), Nd ^{III} (0.045), Sm ^{III} (0.01)	10	10
10*	La ^{III} (0.04), Th ^{IV} (0.005), Pr ^{III} (0.01), Nd ^{III} (0.036), Sm ^{III} (0.003)	5	4.7

*Sample composition corresponding to Australian Amonazite.

^aFigure in brackets indicates the amount of metal ion in mg.

non-interfering. However, phosphate and oxalate cause interference. Amongst the cations, in 10 ml aqueous volume, As^{III}, Ce^{IV}, Os^{VIII} (1 mg each); Mn^{II}, Sb^{III}, Cr^{VI}, Re^{VII},

Table 3. Comparison of the proposed method of determination of cerium(III) with the existing methods

Sl. no.	Aqueous conditions	(i) λ_{max} (nm) (ii) Extractant	Molar absorptivity (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹)	Interfering ions	Ref.
1.	Ce ^{III} , pH 3.1 <i>p</i> -Acetylarsenazo	(i) 670 nm (ii) –	?	EDTA, oxalic acid have to be used as masking agents to check interference of other ions	15
2.	Ce ^{III} , pH 6.9–7.5 3,4,5-Trimethoxy-4'-Me-dibenzoylmethane	(i) 410 nm (ii) –	1.7×10^3	?	16
3.	(i) Ce ^{III} , pH 7.0 1,3-Phenylenediamine bisazoacetylacetone (ii) Ce ^{III} , pH 7.5 1,3-Phenylenediamine bisazoacetylacetone (iii) Ce ^{III} , pH 8.0 1,3-Phenylenediamine bisazoacetylacetone (iv) Ce ^{III} , pH 8.5 1,3-Phenylenediamine bisazoacetylacetone	(i) 573 nm (ii) – (i) 533 nm (ii) – (i) 511 nm (ii) – (i) 638 nm (ii) –	2.58×10^4 2.43×10^4 2.39×10^4 2.28×10^4	S ₂ O ₃ ²⁻ , CN ⁻ , C ₂ O ₄ ²⁻ , CH ₃ COO ⁻ , tartrate, malonate have to be used as a masking agents for checking interference of a large number of foreign ions	17
4.	Ce ^{III} , pH 5.5 Triethylene tetraamine hexaacetic acid	(i) 279 nm (ii) –	8.18×10^2	?	18
5.	Ce ^{III} , HNO ₃ –H ₂ SO ₄ medium (NH ₄) ₂ S ₂ O ₈ , Ag as catalyst	(i) 380 nm (ii) –	1.2×10^3	Interfering ions have to be removed by precipitation	19
6.	Ce ^{III} , pH 8.5 3-Hydroxy-2-(2'-thienyl)-4H-chromen-4 one	(i) 430 nm (ii) –	4.4×10^4	Ti ^{IV} , W ^{VI} , Cr ^{III} Proposed method around 20 cations at μ g level and several anions are non interfering	

Pd^{II}, Pt^{IV}, Ru^{III}, Se^{IV} (0.5 mg each); Bi^{III}, Ir^{III}, Au^{III}, Fe^{II}, Fe^{III}, La^{III}, Nd^{III}, Pr^{III}, Eu^{III} (0.1 mg each); Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, U^{VI}, Zr^{IV}, Ta^V, Th^{IV}, V^V, Mo^{VI} (0.05 mg each); Tb^{III}, Dy^{III}, Gd^{III}, Y^{III}, Sm^{III}, Ho^{III} (0.01 mg each); are not found to show any absorbance under the conditions of the procedure. However, Ti^V, W^{VI}, Cr^{III}, cause interference.

Spectral studies :

The absorption maximum of the Ce^{III}-HTC complex lies at 430 nm, where the blank prepared in an analogous manner has the minimum absorbance value. Beer's law is obeyed in the range 0–1.2 $\mu\text{g Ce ml}^{-1}$ and thereafter, it starts deviating from linearity. The optimum concentration range that can be measured accurately, as evaluated from Ringbom plot¹⁴, is 0.3–1.0 ppm of cerium. Molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity of the complex are $4.4 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.0032 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$, respectively.

Stoichiometry of the complex :

Equimolar solutions of cerium and HTC reagent (0.0005 M) are employed to determine the metal to ligand ratio in the complex by Job's method¹⁵ of continuous variations as modified by Vosburgh and Cooper¹⁶. The result reveals 1 : 2 stoichiometry. The absorbance values are measured at 430 and 450 nm.

Conclusion : The proposed spectrophotometric method for the determination of cerium is simple, rapid, quite sensitive and free from the interference of a large number of metal ions. The validity of the method is tested by analyzing different samples of varying composition as given in Table 2. The results obtained are quite compatible with the amount of metal ion initially added to the sample and reproducible. The method compares favorably with the existing methods in respect of molar absorptivity and selectivity (Table 3).

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